

Davronova Asila Yusuf qizi

Student of the Faculty of Foreign Philology of Termiz State University

Abstract: We know that in teaching foreign languages, teaching with interactive methods and methods is important. This article talks about modern and interactive methods of teaching English.

Keywords: technological tools, modern technology, pedagogical technologies, CEFR, modern methods, foreign language.

In today's rapidly developing age, science and technology are growing rapidly. Progress is being made in every field. In particular, great changes and significant progress are being made in science. Delivery of each subject to students using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education. Especially after the adoption of the decision of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov dated December 13, 2012 PQ 1875, the attention to teaching and learning foreign languages in our country increased even more. A new stage, a new era has begun in the teaching of foreign languages in our country. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools is required during the course of foreign language classes. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It also provides for increasing the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological

tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In today's rapidly developing age, science and technology are growing rapidly. Progress is being made in every field. In particular, great changes and significant progress are being made in science. Delivery of each subject to students using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education. Especially after the adoption of the decision of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abdug'aniyevich Karimov dated December 13, 2012 PQ 1875, the attention to teaching and learning foreign languages in our country increased even more. A new stage, a new era has begun in the teaching of foreign languages in our country. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools is required during the course of foreign language classes. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It also provides for increasing the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer,

player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process, including: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons; — it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method; - CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. In the process of globalization, it is difficult to imagine our life without the Internet. It is considered one of the most effective ways to use it effectively in the process of learning and teaching a foreign language. You will have the opportunity to communicate with people who speak a foreign language through the Internet. You can improve writing practice by writing letters via e-mail. It is the most important issue to bring modern communication technologies into the educational process, to use them purposefully and correctly, to increase the student's interest in a foreign language, and to increase the effectiveness of teaching. Through this, the opportunity to use innovative technologies of education will be created and the demand will increase. Today, there are several different methods of innovative educational technologies. If they use wide and different methods to cover the topic in classes, the effectiveness of the lesson will be high and the increase of students' interest in the lesson will be ensured. It is intended to increase the effectiveness of education by introducing innovations into the educational process and implementing them. The use of various role-playing and action games in the teaching of foreign language classes increases the interest in the lesson and language learning. It helps students to communicate with others by working in pairs or small groups.

In today's modern education, the demand for interactive methods, innovative technologies, information technologies to support the educational process is growing day by day. One of the main reasons for this is that in contrast to traditional education until now, when using modern methods, the necessary conditions are being created for the development, formation, and education of the student's personality. The place and role of modern methods and innovative technologies is huge. There are several effective

ways to teach foreign languages, especially English. In particular, in the course of the lesson, you can use video clips, dialogues, movies or cartoons, tape recorders and CDs, which are considered a more traditional method. The use of these technical tools ensures that the process of learning a foreign language is more interesting and effective for students. The importance of modern methods in teaching a foreign language is incomparable. In this place, several methods that are widely used nowadays are being used.

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